

APPLICATIONS OF ADVANCED MATERIALS TO ROBOTIC DESIGN: THE FREEDOM-7 HAPTIC HAND CONTROLLER

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SUMMARY: Advanced composite materials have many potential benefits in a robotic design application. For the Freedom-7 haptic hand controller, two composite components are proposed. First, the stage 3 linkage is replaced by a small diameter commercially available carbon fiber tube with bonded metal inserts. Second, a composite box-beam structure is proposed to replace the existing aluminum effector arm. Finite element models are used to evaluate the proposed changes. The bond geometry parameters for the composite tube/aluminum insert interface is optimized for minimum weight. Comparisons are drawn between a proposed aluminum box-beam effector arm and a composite arm. Analysis shows an increase in lowest resonant natural frequency, an increase in stiffness and a decrease in overall weight of the composite arm over the aluminum arm. The result of this work is a lighter stiffer hand controller.

KEYWORDS: composite application to robotics, robotic design, finite element modeling, haptic control, force-feedback, bonding, modal vibration, optimization.

INTRODUCTION

Advanced robotic applications have two ever-present performance concerns: inertia reduction and increased stiffness. In most cases, these seem to be opposing criteria. To lower the manipulator inertia, robot links need to be light and slender. However, stiffness requirements ask for links to be heavy and robust. Often, an inadequate compromise has to be made between these two requirements when designers restrict themselves to traditional materials. Many robot designers try to circumvent the problems associated with traditional materials by enhancing the control structure of a manipulator. However, due to the inevitable trade-off between stiffness and inertia and the fundamental limits on what can be achieved by control, the field of robot design is being opened up to advanced composite materials. The high stiffness-to-weight ratio and the opportunity to precisely tailor properties such as stiffness, damping and thermal expansion obtainable with the advanced materials of today make them ideally suited to applications in the robot industry.

Figure 15: Translation Stage Schematic

Until recently, there have been few applications of advanced materials in the robotic industry due to a lack of adequate design tools and unfamiliarity of designers with the materials themselves. One major drawback to the application of these materials is the inevitable metal composite interfaces that arise at the joints of the manipulator. Composite materials do not easily accept bearing fittings or the attachment of drive assemblies.

The Freedom-7 consists of the development of a 7-DOF force feedback haptic hand controller for virtual and teleoperated environments. The hand controller consists of a 3-DOF translation stage (figure 1) and a 4-DOF rotational distal stage. Haptic devices, by their nature requiring interaction with the human hand's sense of touch, require high acceleration capability, which translates directly into the lowest possible link inertia for a given actuating capability [1]. Due to a user's limited ability to absolutely locate points in space, precision in displacement conditions on the end effector has little bearing on the effectiveness of a haptic device [1]. Therefore, the minimum allowable link stiffness is determined by the lowest structural resonant frequency.

The Freedom-7 has several design difficulties inherent in the original aluminum prototype. To reduce the inertia felt by the operator, the links have to be made very slender and light. A low modulus metal such as aluminum cannot provide the stiffness necessary to meet the frequency requirements. The lowest resonant natural frequency of the structure has to be above 200 Hz [2], for simulating contact with a rigid wall in a virtual environment.

Another consideration is that the distal stage is driven by a series of high modulus polymeric fiber bundles that run through a series of pulleys mounted on the translation stage to a fixed motor assembly. In the aluminum prototype, these strings were completely exposed. Such a configuration is clearly unacceptable for a production unit. A composite box-beam structure is proposed both as a structural member and as a protective cover for these strings. With proper choice of the layup material and fiber orientation, the superior stiffness and damping capabilities of composite materials can significantly increase the stiffness of this member while reducing its overall weight.

This paper will be divided into two sections. The first section deals with the incorporation of commercially available carbon-fiber tubes and metallic end fittings into the translation stage in the place of the stage 3 linkage (see figure 1). The second section deals with the design of

a carbon fiber box-section that will be used in the place of the effector arm as a structural member as well as a protective covering for the strings used to drive the distal stage.

CARBON FIBER TUBING IN STAGE 3 LINKAGE

There are several unique characteristics of the Freedom-7 that drive the design choices for the translation stage. For instance, the load cases on the individual links are three dimensional. All links must resist bending loads in two directions, as well as tensile and compressive axial loads. This type of loading suggests that the most efficient link cross section would be tubular. The link most open to exploitation of this design is the stage 3 linkage (see figure 1).

The main consideration for the incorporation of carbon fiber tubing into the design of the hand controller is the carbon/metal interface that occurs at the structure joints. The joints of the translation stage are articulated and so require bushing and/or bearing fittings. As such, machined metal inserts are required. The interface between metal and composite materials has been the subject of much research [3,4,5]. The preferred joining method for these two materials is an adhesive bond. The particular adhesives come in many forms with widely varying material properties, and many factors have to be weighed in order to choose the correct adhesive. Often, a more ductile adhesive will give a stronger bond than a stiffer, more brittle adhesive [3]. The geometry of the bond, including adhesive line thickness (l in figure 2), axial penetration length and adherend wall thickness (a in figure 2) are also of primary concern when designing a bonded interface [4].

The requirements for the Freedom-7 design are of an unusual nature. The two dimensional bending moments suggest that the optimal link cross-section be circular, however there is no torque applied axially to the shaft. Therefore design parameters that have been extensively studied for bonding of composite prop-shafts [4] do not apply. Another method for optimizing the bond geometry needs to be determined.

First, some choices had to be made about the general shape of the metal insert. Aesthetics and stiffness requirements would suggest that an internal plug type fitting would be the best solution but, due to the small inner diameter of the tubes in question, this is rather difficult to execute. A choice was made to use a cylindrical metal outer sleeve that could be machined out of a piece of stock material to the correct size to take the bearing fitting. The sleeve wall thickness, the adhesive line thickness and the sleeve machining are left to be determined.

Figure 16: Bond Geometry Dimensions

As an initial attempt to identify the factors that weigh heaviest on the eventual joint strength, a series of finite element models were constructed with varying parameters. Twenty-four finite element tests were made, as summarized in table 1. The referenced dimensions are shown in figure 2, where e is the axial engagement of the composite tube, and a and l have already

been defined. The fillet at the end of the metal insert and the bond fillet are identical in each model, which is a generally accepted configuration for the reduction of peak stresses at the bond edges [5].

Each test was done to determine the maximum principal stress concentration in the overall bond and the stress distribution along the bottom (carbon fiber interface) for a simple tensile load case. The maximum principal and shear stress for each test is shown in table 2, with the referenced stress concentration locations shown in figure 3. Figures 4 to 6 compare the maximum principal stress distribution along the bottom surface of the bond for the variation of a , l , and e individually around the arbitrary median of 2 mm, 0.25 mm and 5 mm respectively.

Table 1 - Variation of Dimensions for Finite Element Tests

Test Number	a (mm)	l (mm)	e (mm)
Tests 1.1-1.4	2.0	0.25	5.0
Tests 2.1-2.4	0.5	0.25	5.0
Tests 3.1-3.4	4.0	0.25	5.0
Tests 4.1-4.4	2.0	1.0	5.0
Tests 5.1-5.4	2.0	0.05	5.0
Tests 6.1-6.4	2.0	0.25	10.0
Tests 7.1-7.4	2.0	0.25	3.0

Figure 17: Stress Concentration Locations

Figure 4: Variation of Maximum Principal Stress due to Bond Detachment

Table 2: Summary of Maximum Principal Stress Values

	Test 1.1	Test 1.2	Test 1.3	Test 1.4	Test 2.1	Test 2.2	Test 2.3
Max. Principal	1.50×10^4	1.16×10^4	1.22×10^3	1.34×10^3	1.67×10^4	1.18×10^4	1.46×10^3
Location	A	B	D	D	A	B	D
	Test 2.4	Test 3.1	Test 3.2	Test 3.3	Test 3.4	Test 4.1	Test 4.2
Max. Principal	1.67×10^3	3.96×10^3	4.34×10^3	9.96×10^2	1.16×10^3	3.29×10^3	2.37×10^3
Location	D	A	B	D	D	A	B&C
	Test 4.3	Test 4.4	Test 5.1	Test 5.2	Test 5.3	Test 5.4	Test 6.1
Max. Principal	1.89×10^3	1.89×10^3	9.87×10^3	6.96×10^3	1.23×10^3	2.06×10^3	1.08×10^4
Location	D&C	D&C	A	B	D&F	D	A
	Test 6.2	Test 6.3	Test 6.4	Test 7.1	Test 7.2	Test 7.3	Test 7.4
Max. Principal	1.84×10^3	6.69×10^2	7.55×10^2	1.11×10^4	8.45×10^3	1.39×10^3	1.64×10^3
Location	B	D	D	A	B	D	D

Each finite element test has similar configurations depending on the test number. For example, test 1.1 and test 1.4 are the same mesh exactly except that the bond has been broken away from the end of the aluminum insert (BD in fig.3). Tests 1.2 and 1.3 are similar to 1.1 and 1.4 in that the a , l , and e values remain constant but a chamfer has been introduced to the end of the carbon fiber tube (BF in fig.3). As well, test 1.2 has a complete bond with the aluminum insert while in test 1.3 it has once again been broken between the epoxy and the insert end. As we can see in figure 4, the effect of breaking the bond between the epoxy and the end of the tube removes the huge peak stress that can be observed at that interface (A) in test 1.1. The peak stress is transferred to point D (see figure 3) and, as noted in table 2, is reduced by an order of magnitude.

Figure 6: Variation of Maximum Principal Stress due to bond Line Thickness

Figure 5 shows the variation in the distribution of the maximum principal stress at the bottom of the bond due to a variation in a from 0.5 mm to 4.0 mm. The maximum principal stress is reduced along the whole length of the bond with increasing adherend thickness. However, the stresses are not very sensitive to this parameter.

Figure 5: Variation of Maximum Principal Stress due to Adherend Thickness

Figure 8: Max. Principal Stress Contour With Bond Fillet

Figure 6 shows the effect of increasing bond line thickness (l) from 0.05 mm to 1.0 mm. The magnitude of the stresses are more sensitive to this parameter, as seen in the changes of the principal stresses at points A and C.

Figure 7: Max. Principal Stress Contour Without Bond Fillet

The axial engagement, e , is varied from 3.0 mm in tests 6.1-6.4 to 10 mm in tests 7.1-7.4. The maximum principal stress in the bond increases with the decreasing e [see Table 2]. For test 7.4, the maximum principal stress is 1.64 MPa, and decreases to 0.75 MPa in test 6.4 [Table 2].

Figures 7 and 8 compare the effect of adding a fillet to the end of the carbon fiber tube. Figure 7 shows the maximum principal stress contour in the bond near the end of the carbon tube. The contour shown in figure 8 shows the maximum principal stress contour in the same area with the addition of a bond fillet on the carbon tube (FB in Figure 3). The effect on the location of the peak principal stress is zero and the effect on the stress distribution is negligible. The same can be observed in the peak stress summaries given in table 2. The effect of introducing a fillet is negligible compared to the effect on the bond strength of breaking the contact with the end of the insert.

Figure 9: Maximum Principal Stress Distribution in Bond Material due to Bending Load

It is necessary to determine the factors that will contribute to optimizing the bond geometry while minimizing the total mass of the bond. The three main conclusions that can be drawn

from the parameter variation performed are: 1. maximum principal stress decreases with increase in bond length, 2. bond stress decreases with increase in adherend thickness, and 3. there is a peak in maximum principal stress with the decrease in bond line thickness somewhere between 0.25 and 0.05 mm. To minimize weight, an optimal bond geometry would have evenly distributed stresses with magnitudes as high as possible without failure. As a result, recommendations can be made for the final bond geometry. To minimize weight, ideally the bond length should be kept as short as possible, and the adherend wall thickness should be decreased, yet the bond line thickness must lie between 0.25 mm and 0.05 mm. However, a longer bond length is recommended in [6] for strength in bending so e is chosen to be 10.0 mm, a as 1.0 mm and l as 0.1 mm. These dimensions were used to construct a three-dimensional finite element model that was subjected to a bending load simulating an encounter with a limit stop. According to [7], the maximum load by one finger is approximately 40 N. The maximum load can be safely set at 80 N. The lever arm for the stage three linkage is 150 mm, and the offset for the limit stop is approximately 10 mm. The resultant maximum transverse load on the metallic end fitting is (for the purposes of a worst case scenario finite element analysis) 6×10^5 mN spread over seven nodes. The stress contours in the bond material are shown in figure 9. There is good distribution of the peak stress all along the edge of the bond, and the entire bond length is under stress. The ultimate strength of the epoxy is 20.3 MPa[8]. The maximum principal stress in the model is 16.7 MPa. The bond shows a design safety factor of 1.22. The design in this configuration is considered to be optimized.

CARBON FIBER BOX-BEAM IN EFFECTOR ARM

Tailoring of material properties in a box beam section has been the subject of many research papers [6,9-13]. The benefits of using a laminate box-beam for a robotic link are two-fold: first, weight reduction reduces actuator load and manipulator inertia and second, tailoring of material properties allows accurate control of stiffness and material damping, giving designers control over the natural frequency of the manipulator linkages [12,13].

The overall dimensions (inner, outer and length) of the box section that will be used for the effector arm (see figure 1) were defined by interference requirements with the distal stage workspace and the string rotations. Therefore, stiffness requirements for the link are obtainable by varying the material orientation only. The cross section dimensions of the box beam are 60 mm height by 30 mm width. The layup used is a combination of woven and unidirectional material, $[0 / (0/90)_3]^T$, of Advanced Composites Group LTM25 graphite-epoxy[14]. In this case, the (0/90) group represents one layer of woven material. The model will be used to verify the potential benefits in a prototype effector arm. As such, the layup was chosen to represent the materials on hand and the manufacturing concerns. The layup was determined by a finite element iterative method, progressively adding material in stiffer orientations until the required stiffness was reached.

Table 3: Summary of Comparison Between Box Beams

	Aluminum Arm	Composite Arm
Max. Deflection Vertically	1.50×10^{-2} mm	1.37×10^{-2} mm
Vertical Natural Freq.	552 Hz	728 Hz
Horizontal Natural Freq.	[186 Hz]	221 Hz
Total Weight	127 g	82 g

Initially, a hand lay-up around an internal removable mold was considered, but then rejected due to the poor quality external surface finish obtainable. For prototyping purposes an external split mold with an internal bag was used with a hand lay-up of cross plies to obtain the required stiffness and surface finish for the prototype. A single unidirectional ply is used on the outer surface of the box beam to create a smooth exterior surface finish, and to allow for easy layup procedure on the external mold. For more accurate tailoring of properties, including material damping, a filament wound part would be the ideal solution.

Finite element models of the composite arm (including the metal fittings required for attachment) and the proposed aluminum arm were constructed. The specifications for the motors show a maximum torque capability of 1 N·m. With the effector arm length of 200 mm, the maximum output force at the end effector is 5 N. For the purposes of comparison in the finite element model, we will use a maximum end load of 10 N. The maximum deflection of the end of the box-beam and the first natural frequency in bending is compared to the maximum deflection and lowest mode observed in the proposed aluminum arm in table 3. The composite arm showed an 8.67% decrease in the maximum deflection over the proposed aluminum arm in the vertical mode, with an overall weight decrease of 35.43%. The natural frequencies of the composite arm increased 31.88% and 18.82% in the vertical and horizontal modes respectively. Note that the aluminum arm failed to meet the frequency requirement of 200 Hz in the horizontal mode.

CONCLUSIONS

Upon examination of the original configuration of the aluminum prototype for the haptic hand controller, two areas were selected for exploitation of the benefits of advanced materials. First was the stage 3 linkage, which was redesigned as a circular cross-section composite tube bonded to two aluminum end fittings. Second was the effector arm, which was redesigned as a composite box section for the dual purpose of creating a structural entity and protecting the distal stage strings from user interference.

An optimum geometry was determined for the bonding of a circular cross-section composite tube to an aluminum cap end fitting, to be loaded in both tension and bending in two dimensions. The geometry was optimized for weight by reducing the material in the bonded entities to a minimum, while achieving a minimum factor of safety for the maximum principal stress in the epoxy.

A composite box-section beam was proposed as a stiffer, lighter alternative to a reinforced aluminum clad box section forearm. The composite box section showed a higher stiffness in both bending directions, an increase in the lowest resonant natural frequency, combined with a weight savings of 35.43%.

The result of this work is the foundation for the design of a lighter, stiffer translation stage for the 7 DOF haptic hand controller.

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